

Portfolio of Compositions

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NUI MAYNOOTH
Ollscoil na hÉireann Má Nuad

MA Music Composition
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Nine Waves

for Soprano
&
Clarinet

c. 9 mins.

Ben McHugh(2011/12)

Nine Waves

For Soprano and Clarinet – Text

<p>1 = {Ripples, at hand at feet Slip, into sleep}</p>	<p>4 = {interact}</p>	<p>7 = {Take Care to oscillate}</p>
<p>2 = {Curve, line, break, interrupt Dips create a texture that lakes a current space. Waves...high energy}</p>	<p>5 = {Something happened, ...under... we are ripples of our neighbour ...without...}</p>	<p>8 = {Compress, an energy of influence. ...Streamed through a thousand imaginings of frozen fluidity, samples of our space...}</p>
<p>3 = {...like snow, clouded, distinct. ...over... out from the centre}</p>	<p>6 = {fluidity as colour collections of clouded drops, it dropped.}</p>	<p>9 = {...Forced to be Pooled... Distant}</p>

Clarinet Multiphonics and Microtonal Fingerings

Multiphonic 1: Bb

2: G†

3: E

4: E

5: G#

6: A

7: A

8: G#

Quarternote 1: A †

2: C†

3: B †

4: A †

Score Legend

Voice

p* = Relative Dynamic

x Note heads = Vocal technique
(Explained above stave) Eg. Whisper

Slanted and Diamond Note Heads =
Spoken as Normal

Port. = Portamento, Slides Between
Notes

R~~~ = Rolled R sound with Tongue

Clarinet

Square Note heads(■) = Breath

A = Air

T = Tone

TS = Tongue Slap (Percussive Sta-
catissimo)

Breath Markings √ = inhale

▣ = exhale

p* = Relative Dynamic

Multiphonics and fingerings are taken
from New Directions for Clarinet by
Phillip Rehfeldt (University of Califor-
nia Press, 1994)

Nine Waves

for Soprano & Clarinet

Ben McHugh
Nov./Dec. 2011

^ 2-3"
C 3-4"
| 5-7"

Soprano

♩=68

mf {5} *pp* *mf* *mp* *f* small port.

from throat noise (fry) -----> to tone

So ti ha - - - - pe - - - - pe - - - - ne

Clarinet in Bb

♩=68

{1} air -----> tone -----> air

trill speed trill speed trill speed

lip pressure (bend) mostly air tongue slap

*p** *mf** *mp* *sfz* *f* *p* *mp* *ppp* *p* *sf* *mp*

Sop.

10

mp *p* *mf* *p** *f* *sfz* *p** *f** *ppp*

high whisper -----> to tone

at usual speaking pitch

rit. -----> whisper

un - de ...we are... ...i - - - - th - - - - out... wi- ou...

(or lowest note)

Cl.

trill

air -----> tone

lip pressure

rit. -----> whisper

ppp *p* *ppp* *p* *p* *f* *mp* *mp* *mf* *n*

a tempo

Sop. 17 {4} *p* *sf* Closed mouth *pp* < *p* > *pp* *p* *mf* *mp* *mf*

I - te Mmm... Oh Oh I - te i - te in - ...rip - ples...

Cl. {9} *f* *mp* < *f* > *mf* *fp* *p* *mp* *f* > *mp* *mf* *pp*

25 *mp* *pp* < *mp* > *pp* closed mouth ---> open *pp* < *mp* > *pp* *mp** *f**

te - te - mmm - ah a - - - c - t

Cl. *f* *mf* > *p* *pp* < *p* > *sfz* *p* < *mf* *f* *sfz* *pp* *f* *ppp*

30 *p** *f** whisper -----> tone *mp** *f* > *mp*

In - ter - r - rr - rrr - rrrr ah k t

Cl. *mp* trill dynamic *mp** -----> *f** possible *f* *mp* < *mf* > *p* *ppp* *sf* *mf*

breath dynamic *p**

38 *f* *mp* *mf* whsp. *pp* *p*

Sop. *flu - i i - - ty flu flu - i - di - i t as*

lip pressure →

Cl. *{2}* *sf mp* *flz.* *mp < f* *sfz mp* *3* *f mp < f* *> p* *air → tone* *3* *air*

45 *mf 3* *sf* *mf* whsp.

Sop. *co - lo - - co - le - ti of lou - de dro it - it dropped*

Cl. *flz.* *p* *fp >* *fp* *lip* *pp* *ff* *mf* *p* *sf*

52 whsp. *mp* *f** *mp* *f*

Sop. *as colour collections of clouded dropps like snow ...of... lou - de di - sti - o -*

Cl. *f* *{8}* *E* *mf < ff >* *pp < mf* *p* *f*

60

Sop. *mp* {5.1}

o - ou - t ah from the centre mmm li no so - so -

Cl. *mf* *<f>* *sf* *mf* *pp* *mf* *f* {5.1}

67

Sop. *f* *mp* {7} *mf*

some - - thing ha - - pen ...un - der... ...with - out... ...with - out... take

Cl. *mf* *ff* *mf* *p* *f* {3}

74

Sop. *mp* *p* *mf* *p*^{*} whsp.

care to o ...our... o o ci ci late

Cl. *>p* *mf* *f* *mp* *p*^{*} *<mf>* *P*^{*} *f* *mp* *<f>* *slap* *sfz*

G# R G#

82 Sop. ...neigh - bour... o cu cu r rrrrrr ve line break

Cl. *f* *ff* *p* *f* *mp* *f* *p* *mf* *pp* *sf*

Annotations: {2} *mp*, *R* *mf*, *Bb* tr, *E*, {7} flz.

90 Sop. in - ter - rrrrrr rupt di cr a te t la

Cl. *p* *ppp* *p* *mf* *mf* *p* *n*

Annotations: *a* *t*, *tr*, *n*

95 Sop. la a cr r spa waves high en - er - gy co - pre

Cl. *f* *p* *mf*

Annotations: {4}, ord. 3, 3, {8}, 3

99 Sop. *pp* *ppp* *mf* *mp* {1}

ss sss i space rip-ples

Cl. *f* *mf* *f* *ff* *f* *sfz f** *p* *mf**

gradually change fingering

3 3 3 5 a---t

105 Sop. *mf* *f* *p* *mp*

a - fi - slip in - to sleep

Cl. *mf* *f* *p* *f* *sfz* *mf* *p* *f* *mp* *f* *mp* *f*

B $\flat$ tr R

{6} 6 3

112 Sop. *f* *mf* *mf* *rit.* *mf*

forced! to be pooled... dis-tant.

Cl. *ff* *ff* *f* *mf* *f* *pp** *mf** *p* *pp** *n*

G# E B $\flat$ tr A B $\flat$ tr B $\flat$ tr

flz. flz. rit. a---t

So Calm, So...

for Solo
Voice

c. 6 mins.

Ben McHugh(2012)

So Calm, So...

Supplementary Text

- I: But necromancy, the flag and flying banner, blown hither and thither by the winds, is the guide of the silly multitude, which constantly bears witness with gaping wonder to the countless effects of this art; and whole books are written which declare that incantations and spirits are efficacious and speak without tongues and without vocal organs, without which it is impossible to speak, and carry the heaviest weights, raising tempests and rain and transforming men into cats, wolves and other beasts, although they who affirm such things are the first to be transformed into beasts.
- II: And certainly if such necromancy existed, as is believed by lower intellects, there is nothing on the earth which would be so effectual both as regards the service and detriment of man; because if it is true that this art has the power to disturb the calm serenity of the atmosphere, changing it into night and producing sparks and winds, with fearful thunder and lightnings that fly through the darkness, and overthrowing high buildings with violent winds and uprooting forests and striking armies and shattering and overwhelming them, and producing, in addition to this, devastating storms which rob the peasants of the fruits of their toil, what kind of warfare is there so deadly to the enemy?
- III: Who in naval warfare can be compared with him who commands the winds and generates storms which ruin and sink any fleet whatsoever?

Leonardo Da Vinci,
Against Necromancy N. 103,
Thoughts on Art and Life (1452-1519),
Trans. Maurice Baring (1906).

Score Legend

Voice

Multiphonic

Outward

Inward

Duration of rest in seconds

Lowest Vocal Pitch

VIX

for Solo Mixed
Percussion

c. 7 mins.

Ben McHugh(2012)

VIX

Legend

The legend defines the notation for various percussion instruments across two staves: Percussion (Right) and Percussion (Left). The notation includes specific symbols for Cymbals (Crash & China), Gongs, Brake Drums, Temple Bells, Home-Made Wood Blocks, Toms, Log Drum, Cow Bells, and Wooden Planks.

Percussion (Right)

- Cymbals (Crash & China): Represented by two vertical bars.
- Gongs: Represented by 'x' and 'x' with a horizontal line above.
- Brake Drums: Represented by a diamond with a downward-pointing stem.
- Temple Bells: Represented by a circle with a horizontal line above.
- Home-Made Wood Blocks: Represented by a square with a vertical stem.
- Toms: Represented by a solid black circle.

Percussion (Left)

- Log Drum: Represented by a square with a vertical stem.
- Cow Bells: Represented by a diamond with an upward-pointing stem.
- Wooden Planks: Represented by a triangle with an upward-pointing stem.

- || Drum Sticks
- ⊗ Hot Rods
- ∨ Brushes
- ⊡ Xylophone
- ⊡ Rubber
- ⊡ Marimba
- ⊡ Timp
- ⊡ Hands
- ⊡ Bow

VIX

for Solo Percussion

Ben McHugh
(April/May 2012)

♩ = 90 freely, floating

Percussion

f *pp* *mf* *fpp* *ppp*

damp 3" clockwise rub slower (with dynamic)

7 *f* *pp* *mf* *pp* *ppp* *mf* 4:5 5" *ff* 5 6"

15 **Quicker** (*♩ = 102*) *p* *pp* *f* *p* *pp* *f*

22 *flurry* *f* *p* *rit.* 5" *p* *mf* *f*

The score is written for two staves in 4/4 time. It includes various percussion techniques indicated by icons: Drum Sticks, Hot Rods, Brushes, Xylophone, Rubber, Marimba, Timp, Hands, and Bow. Dynamics range from *ppp* to *ff*. Performance instructions include 'freely, floating', 'damp', 'clockwise rub', 'slower (with dynamic)', 'Quicker' (tempo change to 102), and 'flurry'. The piece is divided into measures 1-6, 7-14, 15-21, and 22-28.

Slower

(♩ = 90)

26

rub sim. *ppp* *p* *mp*

33

mf *ff* *p* *pp*

40

close to bell *mf* *mp* *pp* sim.

47

mp

Slightly Quicker

53 (♩ = 96)

pp 3 3 3 3 3 3 f 3 3 3 3 3 3 pp 3 3 3 3 3 3 f 3 3

mf

58

3 3 3 3

pp f f mp p mf rub

6

64

rub 5'' swish

mp p pp 7

70

f 3 3 3 3 5

76

Musical score for measures 76-82. The top staff features a melody with a triplet of eighth notes marked *mf* and a dynamic increase to *f*. The bottom staff has a bass line with a triplet of eighth notes marked *ff* and a dynamic increase to *f*. A hairpin crescendo is shown between the staves.

83

Much Slower
(♩ = 60)

Musical score for measures 83-89. The tempo is marked "Much Slower" with a quarter note equal to 60. The top staff includes a triplet of eighth notes marked *spp*, a 4-measure rest, and a "swish" effect. The bottom staff has a 6-measure rest and a "bowed" effect. The section ends with a dynamic of *p*.

90

Musical score for measures 90-96. The top staff has a triplet of eighth notes marked *p* and *mf*, and a dynamic of *p*. The bottom staff has a dynamic of *p* and a "bowed" effect.

97

Musical score for measures 97-103. The top staff has a dynamic of *p*. The bottom staff has a triplet of eighth notes marked *mf*.

101 floating 12 mp mf fp mp to swish

pp mp mf fp mp

voice mp

"...mmm..."

107 f pp ff

f pp ff

ff

110 mf p pp f p

mf p pp f p

ff

6

Performance time c. 7-8'

Zdaleka

for Flute &
Piano

c. 2 mins.

Ben McHugh(2011/12)

Zdaleka

for Flute & Piano

Ben McHugh
2011/12

Note Heads

- ▲ = Tongue Slap (flute)
- = Air/Breath (flute)
- ◇ = Harmonic (piano)

Static, but not rushed

3/4 Air

Flute

Piano

♩ = 70

8^{vb}-----

f mp ppp

Static, but not rushed

♩ = 70

mp f

harm.

8^{vb}-----

f ppp sff

8^{vb}-----

Fl.

Pno.

7

p mf f mp

harm.

8^{vb}-----

sp f 3 sp f sff ppp

8^{vb}-----

8^{vb}-----

Ped.-----

mp

13

Fl. *f* *p* *f* *sfff* *Air* *3*

Pno. *f* *3* *p* *ff* *mp* *f* *8^{va}* *8^{ub}*

Quicker ♩ = 80

Fl. *pp* *f* *pp* *f* *sf* *f* *Tongue slap*

Move lips away from mouthpiece

(force of breath)

Pno. *mp* *8^{va}* *8^{va}* *8^{va}* *8^{va}* *f* *p* *Red.* *Red.*

24

Fl. *mp* *sf* *3* *mf*

Pno. *8^{va}* *harm.* *8^{va}* *8^{va}* *8^{va}* *mf* *8^{ub}* *p* *p* *f* *8^{ub}* *Red.* *Red.* *8^{ub}* *8^{ub}*

Матрёшки

for Bass Clarinet &
Violoncello

c. 9 mins.

Ben McHugh(2012)

Bass Clarinet Multiphonics

Multiphonic 1: F#

2: A

3: F#

4: Bb

5: E

6: D

Score Legend

Bass Clarinet

Square Note heads (■) = Breath/Air

A = Air

T = Tone

TS = Tongue Slap (Percussive, Staccatissimo) notated with wedge shaped note head (▽)

Breath Markings ∨ = inhale

▣ = exhale

p* = Relative Dynamic

Spoken Text =

Multiphonics and fingerings are taken from New Directions for Clarinet by Phillip Rehfeldt (University of California Press, 1994)

Cello

p* = Relative Dynamic

x Note heads = Special technique (Explained above staff) Eg. Bartók pizz.

Bow Pressure

Normal =

Heavy =

Spoken Text =

Fingerboard Sul Pont.

Sul Tasto

Play behind the nut (top of neck)

матрёшки

for Cello & Bass Clarinet

Ben McHugh
(Summer 2012)

A Adagio Sostenuto

♩=50 (♩=25)

Transposed Score

Bass Clarinet in Bb

3/4 air

ts.

spoken B

inhale

pp *mf* *p* *ppp* *p* *ppp* *mf**

Violoncello

bartok pizz. damp LH

arco molto sul pont.

very little pressure

soft(tone) sp.

pressure

bow posit.

hard(scratch)

sul tasto

fff *pppp* *sppp* *fff* *spp*

B

B. Cl.

5

ts.

harm. (unstable)

kc.

ff *pp* *ppp* *mf* *mp* *pp*

Vc.

arco sp.

hp.

scratch

ff *sff* *sff* *pp* *f* *pp*

8

B. Cl. *mp* *p* *mf* *mp* *pp* ☉ внутри 'Vnu - tri'

Vc. *ff* *ppp* *f* *p*

sp. ord. st.

R Eb C# Bbtr Eb

12

B. Cl. *f* *mp*

Vc. *f* *p*

harm. 7 3

16

B. Cl. *p* *mp* *pp* *mp*

Vc. *pizz* *p* *ppp*

bend col legno battuto sp.

22 **C**

B. Cl. *p* *f* *pp* *fff* *mf* *sp* *mf*

Vc. bow side of cello *pppp* *pp* *pp* ord. st. *mf* 3

27 ☹️ Внутренний

'Vnu-tren-niy'

B. Cl. *pp < mp >* *ff* *pp*

Vc. *ppp* *f* *ppp* *p* scratch IV

32

B. Cl. *mp* *f*

Vc. *ff* *p* *p* *f* *pp* B IV

D

B. Cl. ³⁶ *ppp* *toneless* *ppp* *ff sp*

Vc. *f* *p* *f* *mf* *f* *внутри* 'Vnu - tri'

B. Cl. ³⁹ *sf p* *f p* *mf* *teeth on reed* *ff*

Vc. *mp* *f* *mp* *f* *p*

B. Cl. ⁴³ *f* *mp* *ff* *f*

Vc. *ppp* *ppp* *pp* *ppp* *III+II₇* *I* *fff*

rotate bow Right on string(sp.) 45 degrees

47 **E**

B. Cl. *pp* *f* *pp* *ff* *p* *mf* arco col legno battuto

Vc. *pp* *pp < mf > pp* *ppp*

52 **внешний**
'Vnesh - niy'

B. Cl. *f* *sp* *ff* *p* *f* *mf*

Vc. *pp* *f* *ppp*

ord. arco

57 **кц.** *mp* *f* *p* *arco col legno battuto*

B. Cl. *ff* *f* *sp* *1/2 air* *arco col legno battuto*

Vc. *sf* *pp*

63 **F**

B. Cl. *p* *pp* rotate bow Left on string(sp.) 45 degrees *ff* *mp* *f*

Vc. *f* *pp* msp *pp*

Diagram: Eb

67

B. Cl. a -----> t *f*

Vc. sp *pp* *f* ord

'Vnesh - niy'

70

B. Cl. *p*

Vc. *mf* 3